

CORDEX-FPSCONV CPRCM description (v0.1, 2025-04-29)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15280507](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15280507)

model_id	institute_id	Reference(s)	Configuration	Update frequency at lateral boundaries	Nudging	Horizontal resolution	Nesting	Buffer (no. Grid cells)	No. of vertical levels	Radiation scheme	Shallow Convection scheme	Microphysics scheme	Land-surface scheme	Planetary boundary layer scheme	Soil initialization and spin-up (temperature and moisture)	Aerosols	Solar constant	Land use changes	Urban Scheme	Lake model	Greenhouse gases
CCLM5-0-15	CLMcom-JLU	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	Modified COSMO-DE/COSMO-SW	6h or 3h	no	0.0275°	No	23	50	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989 shallow	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	1 year spin-up (1999)	Tanré et al. (1984)	1368.0 W/m ²	No and yes	none	no	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-14 for Evaluation; CCLM5-0-15 for scenario time-slices	CLMcom-KIT	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	modified COSMO-DE	3h	no	0.0275°	yes, from MLIKIP EUR-22 for evaluation, from CORDEX EUR-11 for scenario time-slices	23	50	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	Interpolated from EUR-22/EUR-11 simulations + 1 month additional spin-up	Tanré et al. [1984].	1368.0 W/m ²	no	none	yes, FLAKE	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-15	CLMcom-ZAMG	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	modified COSMO-DE	3h	no [1]	0.0275°	yes, from EUR-11	23	50	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	Interpolated from Euro-CORDEX simulation with same model + 1 month additional spin-up	Tanré et al. [1984]	1368.0W/m ²	no	none	FLAKE	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-15	CLMcom-DWD	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	modified COSMO-DE	3h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11 with CCLM4-8-17	23	50	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	Interpolated from Euro-CORDEX simulation with same model + 1 month additional spin-up	Tanré et al. [1984].	1368.0 W/m ²	no	none	yes, FLAKE	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-8	COSMO-KIT	Schättler et al., 2016, Doms et al., 2011	modified COSMO-DE	6h	no	0.025°	Yes, from EUR-22	23	60	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke Shallow	COSMO bulk microphysics parameterization	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979		Tanré et al. [1984].	1368.0 W/m ²	no	none		RCP8.5
CCLM5-0-9	CLMcom-WEGC	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	CEG100	3h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11 with CCLM4-8-17	26	60	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	Interpolated from Euro-CORDEX simulation + 15 month spin-up	Tanré et al. [1984].	1368.0 W/m ²	no	none	no	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-14	CLMcom-BTU	Keuler et al., 2016	FPSC03	3h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11 with CCLM5-0-9	23	50	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	Interpolated from Euro-CORDEX simulation with same model + 1 month additional spin-up	Tanré et al. [1984].	1368.0 W/m ²	no	none	FLAKE	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-9	CLMcom-CMCC	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	CMCC namelist including TERRA-URB parameterization	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11 with CCLM5-0-9	23	50	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke 1989	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML, with TERRA-URB activated	Louis 1979	1 year spin-up 1999	Tanré et al. [1984].	1368.0 W/m ²	no	yes, TERRA-URB	no	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3
CCLM5-0-9	CLMcom-GUF	Steffeler et al. (2003), Doms and Förstner (2004), Böhm et al. (2006), Rockel et al. (2008)	Modified COSMO-DE/COSMO-SW	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from 0.11°	18	40	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke shallow with reduced activity	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML	Louis 1979	1 year spin-up 1999	Tanré et al. (1984)	1368.0 W/m ²	no	none	FLAKE	
CNRM-AROME4111	CNRM	Caillaud et al. (2021)	cycle 4111	1h	no	2.5km or 0.0227°	Yes, from MED-11 with spectral nudging (SN) for ERAIN or EUR-11 (no SN) for hist and RCP85	21	60	LW: RRTMG, SW: FMR 6bands	PMCC09 (Pergaud et al, 2009)	ICE3 (Pinty et Jabouille, 1998; Bouteloup et al, 2010)	SURFEX/ISBA-3L	Cuxart Bougeault Redelsberger 2000	2 or 3 years spin-up run	Szopa et al. 2013 [2]	CMIP5 solar forcing data	no	yes, TEB	no	CO2, N2O, CH4, CFC11, CFC12 + WV
COSMO-crCLIM	CLMcom-ETH	Leutwyler et al., 2017	GPU version of COSMO, described in Leutwyler et al., 2017	1h	no	0.02°	Yes, from 0.11°	50	60	Ritter and Geleyn (1992)	Tiedtke shallow convection at 12km, explicit at 2km	Doms et al. 2007, Baldauf and Schulz 2004	TERRA-ML with modifications after Schlemmer et al.	Mellor and Yamada 1982	5-year spinup for intermediate step; a few months for 2.2 km (12km and 2km use the same soil model)	Aerocom climatology (Kinne et al., 2006)	1368.0 W/m ²	No	no	no	H2O, CO2, CH4, N2O, O3, CFC12
HCLIM38-AROME	HCLIMcom	Belušić et al., 2020	HCLIM38h1	3h	no	3km	12 km	8	65	Morcrette	EDMFm	ICE3	SURFEX	HARATU	1 year spin-up (1999)	Tegen et al. (1997)	1366 W/m ²	no	TEB	FLAKE	H2O (prognostic), O3 (monthly climatologies), CO2, CH4, N2O, CFC11, CFC12 (RCP8.5)
HCLIM38-AROME	HCLIM-KNMI	Belušić et al., 2020	HCLIM38h1	1h	no	2.5km	Yes, from RACMO2 at 0.11°	8	65	Morcrette	EDMFm	ICE3	SURFEX	HARATU	1 year spin-up (1999)	Tegen et al. (1997)	1366 W/m ²	no	TEB	FLAKE	H2O (prognostic), O3 (monthly climatologies), CO2, CH4, N2O
RegCM4.5	DHMZ	Giorgi et al., 2012	DHMZ-config	6h	no	4km	yes, from EUR-11	14	41	CCSM	no	testing in progress	CLM4.5	Holtslag PBL	1 year spin-up 1999	aerosol radiative forcings are diagnosed. no coupling to dynamic and thermodynamic	CMIP5 solar forcing data http://solarisheppa.geomiar.de/cmip5	no	none	none	CO2, N2O, CH4, CFC11, CFC12 + WV
RegCM4.7	CUNI	Giorgi et al. 2012	ICTP-config with a different microphysics parameterization	6h	no	3km	yes, from EUR-11	40	41	CCSM	Tiedtke shallow	Nogherotto-Tompkins	CLM4.5	Holtslag PBL	1 year spin-up 1999	aerosol radiative forcings are diagnosed. no coupling to dynamic and thermodynamic	CMIP5 solar forcing data http://solarisheppa.geomiar.de/cmip5	no	yes	CLM-default lake model	RCP4.5
RegCM4.7.1	ICTP	Coppola et al. 2021 (https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2020-435)	ICTP-config	6h	no	3km	yes, EUR-11 configuration but rerun with same non-hydrostatic core of RegCM4.7.1	40	41	CCSM	Tiedtke shallow	WSM5	CLM4.5	Holtslag PBL	1 year spin-up 1999	aerosol radiative forcings are diagnosed. no coupling to dynamic and thermodynamic	CMIP5 solar forcing data http://solarisheppa.geomiar.de/cmip5	no	yes	CLM-default lake model	RCP4.5
REMO	GERICS	Jacob et al., 2012	REMO2015-FPS	1h	no	0.0275°	EUR-11	8	49	Morcrette et al. 1986; Giorgetta and Wild 1995	no	Lohmann and Roeckner 1996; Bouteloup et al. 2011	Hagemann 2002; Rechid et al. 2006	Louis 1979	1 year spin-up 1999	Tanré et al. (1984)	1368.0 W/m ²	no	"rock"	no	RCP8.5
UKMO-UM10.1	MOHC	Berthou et al. Clim Dyn. (2017)	PS35	6h(eraint), 3h(hist/rcp8.5)	no	0.0200°	no	24	70	Edwards and Sling	no	Wilson and Ballard (1999)	JULES (total soil depth = 3m)	Boutle et al. (2014) [3]	1 year spin-up from ERA-interim/global model initial fields	climatological aerosol prc	1361 W/m ²	no	JULES urban tile	no	RCP8.5
WRF 3.8.1	BCCR	Skamarock et al. 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	Config6	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	Thompson	Noah-MP	YSU	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5
WRF 3.8.1	NOA-IERSD	Skamarock et al., 2005, Skamarock and Klemp, 2007	Config3	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	Thompson	Noah	MYNN2	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5
WRF 3.8.1	UHOH	Skamarock et al., 2005, Skamarock and Klemp, 2007	Config4 (D)	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-15	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	Thompson	Noah-MP	MYNN2	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG and microphysics see aerosols	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5
WRF 3.8.1	WEGC	Skamarock et al. 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	Config12 (L)	3h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-15	10	50	RRTMG	no; GRIMS only in EUR-15	Thompson 28	Noah	YSU	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5
WRF 3.8.1	IPSL	Skamarock et al., 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	Config5 (E)	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	Thompson 8	Noah-MP	MYNN2	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP8.5
WRF 3.8.1	AUTH-MC	Skamarock et al., 2005, Skamarock and Klemp, 2007	Config7 (BG)	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-15	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	WDM6	Noah-MP	YSU	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5, CO2, N2O, CH4, CFC11, CFC12, +O3+WV
WRF 3.8.1	FZJ	Skamarock et al. 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	Config2 (BB)	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-15	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	Thompson 28	Noah	YSU	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG and microphysics see aerosols	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5, CO2, N2O, CH4, CFC11, CFC12, +O3+WV
WRF 3.8.1	CICERO	Skamarock et al. 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	Config10 (BJ)	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11	10	50	RRTMG	UW (Park and Bretherton, CAM5)	WDM6	Noah-MP	MYNN2	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5
WRF 3.8.1	UCAN	Skamarock et al. 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	Config9 (BI)	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	WDM6	Noah-MP	MYNN2	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	CO2,N2O,CH4
WRF 3.8.1	IDL	Skamarock et al. 2005, Skamarock and Klemp 2007	BD	6h	no	0.0275°	Yes, from EUR-11	10	50	RRTMG	GRIMS	Thompson	Noah-MP	MYNN2	1 year spin-up run (1998) [4]	RRTMG sees aerosols, microphysics do not	1370 W/m ² * eccentricity factor	no	none	no	RCP4.5

No. Note

- [1] yes for ERAinterim to 0.11 in the evaluation run. no for further step to 0.0275 and no for future simulations
- [2] RRTMG and FMR6 see aerosols, microphysics do not. Observation-based climatological aerosols for ERA-Interim (Nabat et al, 2013 : dust, sea salt, organic carbon, black carbon : 2D pattern, monthly variation, no sulfates due to an error in the preparation of the files). Aerosols from Szopa et al. 2013 (dust, sea salt : 2D pattern, monthly variation; organic carbon, black carbon, sulfate : 2D pattern, monthly variation+ trends) for historical and RCP8.5
- [3] 3D scheme based on Smagorinski (1963)
- [4] The spin up (1998) was performed by FZJ (Klaus Goergen) and is common to all WRF configurations

institute_id	institution
AUTH-MC	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Meteorology & Climatology
BCCR	NORCE & Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research
CICERO	Center for International Climate Research
CLMcom-BTU	Chair of Environmental Meteorology, Brandenburg University of Technology (BTU), Cottbus, Germany
CLMcom-CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC Foundation)
CLMcom-DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany
CLMcom-ETH	ETH Zurich, Institute for Atmospheric and Climate Science
CLMcom-GUF	Goethe university Frankfurt
CLMcom-KIT	Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research, Group Regional Climate and Water Cycle /RCWC), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany
CLMcom-WEGC	Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria
CLMcom-ZAMG	Climate Research Departement, Central Institute for Meteorology and Geodynamics (ZAMG), Vienna, Austria
CNRM	Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques, Météo-France, CNRS, Toulouse, France
COSMO-KIT	Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Karlsruhe, Germany
CUNI	Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Atmospheric Physics, Prague, Czech Republic
DHMZ	Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service
FZJ	Institute of Bio- and Geosciences (Agrosphere, IBG-3), Research Centre Juelich, Juelich, Germany
GERICS	Climate Service Center Germany
HCLIM-KNMI	KNMI, Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
HCLIMcom	Collaborative runs of the Danish, Norwegian and Swedish Meteorological (and Hydrological) Institute
ICTP	Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics - Earth System Physics
IDL	IDL - Instituto Dom Luiz Universidade de Lisboa
IPSL	Institut Pierre Simon Laplace, LATMOS, CIMA, CNRS, France
JLU	Justus-Liebig-University Giessen
MOHC	Met Office Hadley Centre
NOA-IERSD	National Observatory of Athens, Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development
UCAN	Instituto de Física de Cantabria (IFCA), CSIC-Universidad de Cantabria, Santander, Spain
UHOH	Institute of Physics and Meteorology, University of Hohenheim
WEGC	Wegener Center for Climate and Global Change, University of Graz, Austria

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Version	Date	Comment
v0.1	2025-04-29	Initial version published on Zenodo